

1 **Myc and Mycbp2 function together with Ndr1 in cells lacking p53 but Mycl functions in cells**
2 **expressing a dominant negative p53 mutation.**

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7 We describe here differences in Myc family gene expression associated with p53 status in cancer cells. In
8 cells lacking p53, Myc and Mycbp2 functioned together with Ndr1. In cancer cells expressing a dominant
9 negative point mutant R175H, Mycl expression was instead most prominent. Myc family genes including
10 Myc gene members associated with neurotrophic activity like Ndr1 are intimately associated with p53
11 status.
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